

Machine and deep learning approaches for monitoring predictive in healthcare

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Abstract. This work focuses on the analysis and development of data analytics and machine learning models in healthcare. Specifically, an overview is given of the state of the art regarding the challenges and opportunities of using big data analytics, machine learning and sensor technologies in healthcare. The different sources of healthcare data and their possible applications are investigated, focusing on the analysis of data relating to patients with heart attacks. This is the leading cause of death in the world today. The aim is to identify possible correlations and patterns in the analysis values of heart attack patients compared to healthy patients in order to highlight possible emerging differences. In addition, supervised machine learning models are trained to classify those at risk of heart attack versus those not at risk, and then identify the best model that achieves the highest accuracy.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, Big Data analytics, Predictive Healthcare, Remote Healthcare systems.

1 Introduction

In this first chapter, we introduce the operational context in which this work was developed. Next, the three main topics concerning Big Data Analytics, Machine Learning, and sensor data are defined and contextualized.

A survey conducted by Deloitte in seven European countries (Denmark, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, and the United Kingdom), interviewing 1800 doctors, showed that 64% of organizations across Europe claim to have increased their use of digital technologies to support new ways of engaging and involving patients, while 65% claim to have increased their use of digital technologies to support the work of healthcare professionals following the COVID-19 emergency. The adoption of these new technologies, however, is not solely explained by the emergency triggered by the health crisis. The same survey also showed that the three technologies most used during the pandemic were electronic medical records (81% in Europe and 69% in Italy), electronic prescription systems (62% on a European basis and 67% in Italy), and online appointment booking platforms (54% on average in Europe).

However, the main challenges in relation to the adoption of these technologies are bureaucracy in the healthcare sector (57.4% at the European level, and in Italy it reaches 64%), the cost of technologies (50.3%), and finding the right technologies (49%). Worthy of note is the research reported by the Deloitte Center for Health Solutions, according to which, by 2040, care will be organized around the consumer rather than around the institutions that drive the entire healthcare system. In particular, the patient will not only have access to detailed information about his or her own health condition but will also own his or her own data and will be able to play a central role in the decision-making process for his or her own well-being.

From 2020 to 2024, investments in digital health have surged significantly. The global market value increased from \$96 billion in 2020 to an expected \$220 billion by 2024. Telemedicine and remote healthcare solutions were major investment areas, driven by the pandemic's need for remote patient care. Artificial intelligence and machine learning also attracted substantial funding, enhancing diagnostics and personalized treatments. Wearables and mobile health applications received increased investments due to their role in real-time health monitoring and proactive healthcare management. This trend reflects a broader shift towards integrating advanced digital technologies in healthcare to improve efficiency and patient outcomes [27][28].

1.1 Big Data Analytics

As reported in [1] and [2], the website of one of the world's largest ICT multinational companies, big data are large and complex datasets, mainly originating from the latest technologies. These data sets are so massive that traditional processing software cannot handle them. However, massive volumes of data can be used to approach problems that could not be confronted before. According to [1], big data are data that exceed the limits of traditional database tools, but the term is also used to define technologies aimed at extracting knowledge and value from data.

As reported in [3], big data analytics refers to the process of collecting and analyzing large volumes of data (big data) to extract hidden information. This analysis process makes it possible to carry out predictive analysis, i.e., to know in advance what is going to happen. This becomes possible because, with a model and enough historical data, it is possible to determine what is going to happen in the near future by means of statistical principles or fundamentals. Based on these predictions, it is then possible to intervene in the future by means of a prescriptive analysis, i.e., the conditions are sought for a certain event to happen. Another definition from one of the world's largest software development corporation states that big data analysis refers to the methods, applications, and tools used to collect, process, and obtain detailed information from various high-volume, high-velocity data sets. Such data can be structured, semi-structured, or unstructured.

Data analysis processes are very important today because organizations, both public and private, can exploit such information to rapidly improve the way they work, think, and deliver value to customers. One example is how a retailer can refine

its targeted advertising campaigns, or how a wholesaler can solve bottlenecks in the supply chain; but also, how a healthcare provider can discover new clinical care options based on trends in patient data. This is precisely one of the cases of analysis that is the subject of the design and experimental part of this discussion.

1.2 Machine Learning

As mentioned in the previous paragraphs, machine learning is one of the techniques used in Big Data Analytics. More specifically, according to [4], machine learning is the science of developing algorithms and statistical models that enable computer systems to perform tasks without explicit instructions, relying instead on models and inference. The goal is to identify data models that can predict outcomes by processing new, unseen data.

Machine learning is a branch of AI and computer science that focuses on using data and algorithms to mimic human learning, gradually improving accuracy. This means that the goal of a machine learning model is to 'learn' from the data it is initially given, and then act autonomously on new data to make predictions, classifications, or prescriptions.

The main areas of application for machine learning are:

- Manufacturing: Supports predictive maintenance, quality control, and innovative research.
- Healthcare: Analyzes data from sensors, wearable devices, and general clinical analyses to support doctors in diagnosis and treatment.
- Entertainment: Gains a better understanding of the audience to offer customized content and optimize production.
- Finance: Improves data analysis and risk prediction, mitigates risks, and helps investors identify new potentially profitable opportunities.

In general, the goal of machine learning is to find a mathematical relationship (typically a function) that links the input data to the output data. Initially, the model does not know this function, but the goal of the algorithm is to identify it. Unlike traditional software development, where you know the input and the function and want to calculate the output, in machine learning, you know the input and output data and aim to find the relationship that connects them. By doing so, the model can operate autonomously on new, unseen data. Thus, instead of programming a system to perform specific operations, you create a model that can autonomously adapt to perform the necessary operations.

1.3 Sensor data

Thanks to recent advances in sensor technologies and wearable devices, several new sources of data are available to provide insights into patients. For example, there are blood pressure bracelets, heart rate monitors and even portable electrocardiogram monitors available for collecting vital parameters and formulating early diagnoses. By means of advances in sensor technologies, various remote health monitoring solutions have been proposed for the management of chronic diseases and wellness in general. While the rapid growth of data from health sensors promises to have a significant impact on healthcare delivery, it also introduces a problem of data overload, both for systems and for stakeholders, who have to consume this data. It is therefore necessary

to integrate these sensing capabilities with data mining and data analytics techniques in order to transform large volumes of data into meaningful and usable information.

Sensors measure physical attributes and produce signals, i.e. time series consisting of ordered measurements. For example, in intensive care, breathing frequencies are estimated from measurements of the patient's chest impedance. The resulting time series signals are used by humans or other sensors and computer systems. The output of the thoracic impedance sensor can be used by an apneas detection system to produce a signal measuring the episodes in which the event occurs. The data elements produced by sensors range from simple scalar values (numerical or categorical) to complex data structures. Examples of simple data elements include measurements such as the hourly average temperature at a given location, emitted by a temperature sensor. Examples of more complex data elements include summaries of vital signs and alarms measured by the sensor of a patient monitor in a medical institution.

The main types of sensors are:

- Physiological sensors: these sensors measure a patient's vital signs or physiological statistics. They were first used to measure the vital parameters of astronauts before appearing in medical institutions in the 1960s. Today, physiological sensors are also available outside the medical context, on pervasive devices; think of the heart rate monitoring applications in smartphones, using its cameras.
- Wearable activity sensors: these sensors measure attributes of the user's overall activity. Examples include accelerometers used to monitor walking. Some shoe manufacturers have equipped many of their running shoes with sensors that can monitor walking or jogging activities. Most smartphones are also equipped with accelerometers and several wellness management applications make use of these sensors.
- Human sensors: humans play a key role in the sensing process. For instance, doctors enter important information about a patient's health status during examinations. Laboratory technicians follow rigorous processes to provide information on blood content. Self-reporting (i.e. the monitoring of health parameters by patients) is also used in the management of chronic diseases such as diabetes.
- Contextual sensors: these sensors are embedded in the environment around the user to measure various contextual properties. Examples include motion detection sensors, audio and video sensors, temperature sensors, and weather sensors.

Some typical use cases include remote patient monitoring systems with sensor mining capabilities for chronic disease management. For instance, these systems can continuously or periodically monitor patient data, such as glucose levels for diabetic patients and ECG for cardiac patients and analyze them to detect significant variations that might indicate changes in the patient's condition. This type of sensor mining capability enables more proactive and personalized management of patient health, improving the timeliness and effectiveness of medical interventions. It is precisely these types of data sensing that form the basis for the data analysis project described later in the discussion.

2 Biomedical Signal

Biomedical signal analysis consists of measuring signals from biological sources, the origin of which lies in various physiological processes. These signals according to their origin, are classified into different types, for example, physiological signals originating from electrical activity in the heart constitute the electrocardiogram (ECG), while those originating from electrical activity in the brain constitute the electroencephalogram (EEG). Biological signals come in many forms: electrical, acoustic, chemical and many others. Analysis of these signals is essential to diagnose pathological conditions and decide on an appropriate course of care. The measurement of physiological signals provides a method of quantitative or relative assessment of the state of the human body. Acquisition of these signals requires the use of appropriate sensors and transducers; acquisition can be invasive or noninvasive; signals are either discrete or continuous, depending on the type of care or severity of a particular disease condition. A key point is that many times the signals acquired by the sensors must be extracted from the raw data so that meaningful information or features can be captured. Processing and interpretation of physiological signals sometimes presents difficulties due to low signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) or interdependence of physiological systems. A classic example can be seen in the case of heart sound measurement. For a normal human subject, the second heart tone, which is created by the closure of the aortic valve followed by the closure of the pulmonary valve, shows subdivision during inspiration but not during expiration; however, subdivision of the second heart tone during both inspiration and expiration could indicate cardiac abnormalities. These interrelationships should be considered when designing a feature extraction algorithm, which sometimes occurs as a step after signal processing.

To improve the accuracy and reproducibility of the measurement, there are several noise reduction techniques. One of the most widely used is PCA, especially for multivariate signal analysis. PCA is applied for data reduction, beat detection, classification, signal separation and feature extraction. PCA can be used for separation of respiratory and non-respiratory segments in an ECG signal. Noise reduction and data compression are closely related, as both require PCA to concentrate the original signal information into a few eigenvectors whose noise level is low. The classification of waveform morphologies in arrhythmia monitoring is another early application of PCA, in which a subset of the principal components serves as features used to distinguish between normal sinus beats and abnormal waveforms, such as premature ventricular beats. A recent application of PCA in ECG signal processing is feature extraction of various waveform properties in order to monitor temporal changes due to myocardial ischemia.

3 Case study: heart attack data analysis

This data analysis model aims to highlight the correlations between blood test values and the presence or absence of a heart attack in a subject. The latter is a serious health problem as it is considered the leading cause of death in the world today. Specifically, more than 1,300 patients are considered of whom (some) blood test values are

available and, as a target, the presence or absence of a heart attack. The CC 4.0 International licensed dataset was used. The following features were identified in the dataset:

- Age: age of the patient
- Gender: gender of the patient
- Impulse: heart rate (normal between 60 and 100 bpm)
- Pressurehigh: systolic pressure (normal between 110 and 130)
- Pressurelow: diastolic pressure (normal between 70 and 85)
- Glucose: blood glucose (normal between 60 and 110 mg/dl)
- Kcm: serum creatine kinase-MB (normal between 0 and 25 IU/L)
- Troponin: tropin (normal if ≤ 0.2 mg/L)
- Target: target variable indicating the presence or absence of a heart attack

The case study has been divided into two sections: the first has the main objective of analyzing the input data to perform the feature selection; the second section has the objective of training some machine learning models that act as classifiers, to recognize the possibility of a heart attack or not, and finally identify the model with the best accuracy. The target variable presents positive cases with a value of 1 and negative cases with a value of 0.

3.1 First section: factorial analysis (PCA)

In the first section, factorial analysis was employed within principal component analysis (PCA) to identify and interpret the fundamental factors driving the relationships among the observed variables in the dataset. Factorial analysis allows for the identification of these underlying factors, which are then quantified through factor loadings. These loadings, calculated using the saturation method [25], reflect the strength of correlation between each observed variable and every underlying factor. By considering the full extent of each variable's association with all factors, the saturation method offers a comprehensive understanding of the relationships between variables and factors.

Once the factors are identified and their associations quantified through factor loadings, PCA is conducted using these loadings instead of the original observed variables. This approach enables the identification of principal components that capture the maximum variance in the dataset, while also accounting for the extent to which each variable is saturated with each factor.

PCA is a powerful multivariate statistical technique that expresses the variability of statistical variables (represented in k dimensions as Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_k) in terms of linear combinations of other variables (Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_k)." It has:

It has:

$$Y_i = \sum_j b_{ij} Z_j \quad (i=1, 2, \dots, k) \quad (3.1)$$

where b_{ij} are constants to be determined. Y_i are called the main components of the variable Z and assuming they are not related to each other ordered by importance, in the explanation of the variability of Z we have:

$$\text{cov}(Y_i, Y_j) = 0 \quad (i \neq j) \quad (3.2)$$

$$V(Y_1) \geq V(Y_2) \geq \dots \geq V(Y_k) \quad (3.3)$$

where cov is covariance and V is variance. Without loss of generality, we can assume that the variables Z_i are standardized, with mean $\mu=0$ and standard deviation $\sigma=1$, to eliminate the influence of the origin and the unit of measurement data, so that it results the following expression:

$$Z_j = (X_j - \mu_j) / \sigma_j \quad (3.4)$$

Also, impose the condition that the overall variance of Z_j is equal to that of Y_i , i.e.:

$$\sum_i V(Y_i) = \sum_i V(Z_i) = k \quad (3.5)$$

At last, suppose that the vectors

$$b_i = (b_{i,1}, b_{i,2}, \dots, b_{i,k}) \quad (3.6)$$

have unit length, i.e., they fulfill the condition:

$$\sum_j b_{ij}^2 = 1 \quad (i=1, 2, \dots, k) \quad (3.7)$$

On account of this, the vectors b_i that maximize the variance of Y_1 , of Y_2 , ..., to Y_k with the constraints (3.3) and (3.4), are the eigenvectors of the matrix C of the coefficients of correlation between the variables Z_j , which correspond to the eigenvalues $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_k$ of C, sorted by non-increasing value. We then have:

$$|C - \lambda I| = 0 \quad (3.8)$$

$$b_i (C - \lambda_i I) = 0 \quad (3.9)$$

where I is the unit matrix. The matrix C is symmetric and positive definite for which the solutions λ_i of the (8) are non-negative and such that their sum (trace of the matrix C) is equal to k. We then have:

$$\sum_i \lambda_i = k \quad (i=1, 2, \dots, k) \quad (3.10)$$

The variance of the i-th component is:

$$V(Y_i) = \lambda_i \quad (3.11)$$

And the contribution of Y_i to the overall variance is:

$$P_i = V(Y_i) / k = \lambda_i / k \quad (3.12)$$

Tables 1, 3, 5 shows the variance values explained according to the main components extracted.

Table 1. Variance values explained on all patients.

F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7
0,20	0,34	0,47	0,60	0,73	0,85	0,95

In the first elaboration all the cases were calculated excluding the target variable, as can be seen in table 2 the substantial correlation is on the variables relative to arterial pressure which express only 20% of the explained variance, in order to reach 95% of the explained variance it is necessary to reach the seventh factor, this means that the other variables are quite independent of each other. Also refer to figure 1 to better visualize the correlation of the variables.

Table 2. Measure of variables correlation on all patients.

Variable T0-1	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7
age	0,007	0,9979	-0,0609	-0,0021	-0,0161	0,0047	-0,0077
gender	0,0006	-0,0328	0,9987	-0,0011	-0,0148	-0,0022	-0,0341
impulse	0,0399	-0,0077	-0,0115	0,0029	0,9965	0,0087	-0,0054
glucose	-0,0006	0,0001	0,0035	-0,0228	-0,0086	-0,9991	-0,0106
pressurehight	0,8941	0,0162	0,0158	0,006	-0,0561	-0,0352	-0,0135
pressurelow	0,8859	-0,0081	-0,0154	0,0095	0,1047	0,0387	-0,0192
kemp	-0,0133	0,0175	0,0172	-0,9993	-0,009	-0,0229	0,0088
troponin	0,03	0,0834	0,0347	0,0091	0,0056	-0,0107	-0,9953

Fig. 1. Correlation chart of the variables against target 0-1

The following elaborations were conducted by first excluding the negative cases and then the positive cases, the results of tables 4 and 6 and graphs 2 and 3 show, as

in the previous elaboration, that only the variables related to the minimum and maximum pressure are correlated with each other, but on both elaborations we still express only 20% of the explained variance, to get to 95% we need to increase the component factors up to 7. Again, the other variables turn out to be quite independent even though the datasets are already classified by reference target.

Table 3. Variance values explained on all patients.

F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7
0,20	0,34	0,48	0,60	0,73	0,85	0,95

Table 4. Measure of variables correlation on target 1.

Variable T1	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7
age	0,0054	0,997	-0,0173	-0,0099	0,0031	-0,0277	-0,0661
gender	0,0062	-0,0668	-0,0276	0,0235	0,0048	-0,0036	0,9968
impulse	0,0392	0,0007	-0,0056	0,0071	-0,9964	-0,0087	-0,0049
glucose	0,005	-0,0029	0,9437	0,3021	0,0005	0,1237	-0,0265
pressurehight	0,8907	0,0231	0,0523	0,0297	0,0575	0,0059	0,0265
pressurelow	0,8832	-0,0168	-0,0491	0,023	-0,1059	-0,0127	-0,0186
kcm	-0,0204	-0,019	-0,0427	-0,0369	0,0088	0,998	-0,0035
troponin	0,0502	0,0459	-0,2602	0,9617	-0,0032	-0,045	0,0266

Fig. 2. Correlation chart of the variables against target 1

Table 5. Variance values explained on all patients.

F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7
0,20	0,35	0,49	0,62	0,74	0,85	0,95

Table 6. Measure of variables correlation on target 0.

Variable T0	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7
age	0,0172	0,9973	0,022	0,0201	0,0211	-0,033	-0,052
gender	-0,0059	-0,0514	-0,0469	0,02	0,0437	-0,0283	0,996
impulse	0,0407	-0,0326	-0,0107	-0,0029	-0,0173	0,9957	-0,0285
glucose	-0,0167	0,0212	0,0237	0,0027	0,9981	-0,0174	0,0434
pressurehight	0,899	0,0178	-0,0221	0,0382	0,0101	-0,0527	0,009
pressurelow	0,8888	0,0018	-0,0174	-0,058	-0,0307	0,104	-0,0134
kcm	0,0332	-0,024	-0,9972	-0,0346	-0,0217	0,0077	0,0464
troponin	-0,016	0,0201	0,035	0,998	0,0023	-0,0031	0,0198

Fig. 3. Correlation chart of the variables against target 0

PCA analysis shows that 6 of the 8 features in the dataset are independent of each other and only 2 out of 8 (high blood pressure and low blood pressure) are correlated.

3.2 Second section ML algorithms

In the second section, three different machine learning algorithms, acting as classifiers, are trained to identify the target class (heart attack or not) from the dataset presented. Specifically, the following supervised learning algorithms were trained:

- Perceptron [24]: a supervised learning technique that is used to predict whether a given sample belongs to one class or another. In more formal terms, one can consider this problem as a binary classification task. It is then possible to define an activation function that takes a linear combination of certain input values and a corresponding vector of weights. If the activation of a particular sample is greater than a certain threshold, it can be predicted to fall into one class, otherwise it will be part of the other. In the perceptron algorithm, the activation function is a piecewise-defined function, which is sometimes called a Heaviside step function. In conclusion this model is particularly suitable for linear binary classification where data are linearly separable.

- Support Vector Machine [23]: is a binary classification method. The algorithm divides the observations in the training data set into two groups. In the case of a two-dimensional space (i.e. two variables), one can think of a simple line separating the two groups. Assume that the points on one side of the line represent the positively coded observations for the outcome variable and those on the other side, the negatively coded observations. The algorithm is designed to select the line that maximizes the distance between the two observations, called 'support vectors'. The support vectors, one on each side, are the points closest to the line. The selected line is called the 'decision boundary'. As with all other learning methods, this optimizes an objective function. In this case, the distance between the support vectors is maximized, measured as the 'geometric margin'; basically, it is the geometric mean of the distance between the observations and the boundary. Obviously, in most cases positive and negative observations are not easily separable. Therefore, there must be a trade-off between maximizing this distance and misclassifying some observations (i.e. placing them on the wrong side of the line).

- Decision Tree [23]: a 'decision tree' is branched with a decision rule at each junction, pointing in one of two directions. There are two types of decision trees: 'classification tree', where the target variable is categorical, usually with two values, and 'regression tree', where the target variable is continuous. Decision trees are among the most popular machine learning algorithms due to their simplicity and consequent easy interpretation. The components of the decision tree are the 'Root' node, i.e. the beginning of the decision tree, which includes all points in the training sample, and the 'Decision' node, i.e. where the tree divides according to a decision criterion. Algorithms for constructing a decision tree usually work top-down, choosing a variable at each step that best divides the set of elements according to the outcome. There are several alternative methods used to define and identify the 'best' method. The splitting algorithm attempts to maximize the 'homogeneity' of the target variable within each of the two resulting nodes. It simultaneously attempts to maximize the difference between them. It also searches for the variable that, when used to subdivide the cases, optimizes the chosen objective function.

The Decision Tree emerged as the most suitable ML model for making predictions from the reference dataset, achieving an accuracy of approximately 98.9%. In contrast, the Support Vector Machine model achieved accuracy rates slightly above 92% and Perceptron model only reached around 75% due to its inability to handle the complexity of the data.

Figure 4 presents the confusion matrix generated by the Decision Tree (DT) model, illustrating the correct (652) and incorrect (8) predictions through a heatmap.

Fig. 4. Confusion matrix

Another method to assess the DT model performance is by the classification report in Table 7 that includes precision, recall, F1-score, and support for each class.

Table 7. Classification report of Decision Tree model

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Target 0	0.98	0.99	0.99	254
Target 1	0.99	0.99	0.99	406
accuracy			0.99	660
macro avg	0.99	0.99	0.99	660
weighted avg	0.99	0.99	0.99	660

4 Conclusion

In this work, we have demonstrated a methodology for analyzing a publicly available dataset and training a machine learning model capable of providing very high performance (98.9% accuracy) in classifying heart attacks.

Literature research [32] indicates that numerous approaches can be used to predict heart disease through data analysis, using both machine learning and deep learning techniques. However, the results often depend on the quality and quantity of the data sources.

To address this problem, we intend to apply the methodology presented here to datasets from a remote healthcare system that includes home medical devices capable of continuously providing a larger number of variables. With this expansion we aim to improve the predictive capabilities of the classifier for more general cases of heart disease, effectively identifying anomalies and flagging potential adverse events well in advance for monitored patients.

The REMOTE project is strongly oriented on this stage, we are preparing all possible actions so that our ideas can be tested.

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